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Comparative Analysis of PS-InSAR and NSBAS Methods for Land Subsidence Monitoring in Urban Coastal Areas

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Abstract: This study investigates the performance and accuracy of two Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) processing methodologies for monitoring land subsidence in North Jakarta, employing the Persistent Scatterer Interferometry SAR (PS-InSAR) and New Small Baseline Subset (NSBAS) techniques. Sentinel-1A imagery was processed to compare the outputs of these approaches in terms of spatial coverage, statistical precision, and computational efficiency. Validation was conducted using the Monte Carlo sampling method and field data from the Balai Konservasi Air Tanah (BKAT). The results indicate that PS-InSAR achieves denser spatial coverage and higher confidence levels, with an average deviation of 7 mm/year and accuracy exceeding 90%. In contrast, NSBAS exhibits advantages in processing efficiency and broader mapping capabilities but generates a higher proportion of data gaps, particularly in urban coastal regions. These findings emphasize the critical role of methodological selection in SAR-based land subsidence assessments and the implications of algorithmic differences on the reliability of subsidence models. The study provides valuable insights for researchers and practitioners in selecting appropriate SAR processing techniques for urban deformation analysis.

Keywords: *Synthetic Aperture Radar, Sentinel-1 A, land subsidence, North Jakarta.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Many studies have looked into the use of Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) to study land subsidence, showing its ability to detect and monitor ground deformation over time (Bagheri-Gavkosh et al., 2021; Kumar et al., 2020; Sukmawati et al., 2021). These studies often focus on developing algorithms that process satellite data to improve the accuracy and reliability of detecting subsidence (Ferretti et al., 2007; Shimada, 2019). SAR applications have been researched worldwide (Golkar et al., 2021; Solórzano et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2022). In the past, processing radar images was a challenging and time-consuming task, especially before modern computer technologies were available (Cruz et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2019). However, even with current advancements, only a few studies have discussed how much computational power and program algorithms affect the quality of results from SAR data. Geospatial technologies like the

Global Positioning System (GPS) and photogrammetry are often used alongside SAR to validate measurements, especially when studying land changes and subsidence (Hu et al., 2019). One major challenge with SAR is the need for powerful computers, especially when analyzing large datasets or studying broad areas over long periods. High-performance computing is essential for managing these tasks since the processing time increases with the area's size and the observation period's length. These challenges highlight the importance of choosing the right methods and resources to ensure accurate and efficient results in SAR-based studies, particularly in areas like North Jakarta Administrative (NJA), which is widely known for its subsidence problems. Although the empirical equations for InSAR have been extensively documented in the literature (Lazecky et al., 2016; Perissin et al., 2016), they tend to differ in detail as the development of specific standard processing is varied; many questions emerge when the approach in empirical equations is either in atmospheric correction or an unwrapping process. When both methods are compared (PS-InSAR and NSBAS), different techniques and algorithms are applied in the analysis. Prior research from other researchers states that NSBAS is more potent for investigation on mountainous and rough topography where vegetation and natural landscapes are more dominant, while PS-InSAR is more advanced and robust for urban monitoring, manufactured construction, and infrastructure investigation (Bui et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021). However, the opposite of what is stated by (Li et al., 2022), where NSBAS measures high coherence points and slow deformation, which is low in vegetated areas but abundant in exposed rock and buildings.

Given these discrepancies, a comparative analysis of different processing approaches is necessary to assess their significance and potential influence on SAR results. There is a concern that the embedded algorithms in SAR processing can yield differing results, even when applied to the same data source, such as Sentinel-1A. Therefore, this study seeks to quantify the deviations between results generated by different InSAR processing methods and develop simulation models to identify an acceptable standard of tolerance (AST) for these discrepancies. To address this research gap, the authors focus on land subsidence as a case study (Abidin et al., 2010). While prior studies have compared PS and SBAS methods globally (Bokhari et al., 2023; X. Chen et al., 2021; Gheorghie & Armaş, 2016; Lazecky et al., 2016; Marwanza et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2021), no case studies have specifically been conducted in Jakarta. Furthermore, the mathematical and statistical approaches to comparing the processing results of these two methods have not been adequately addressed. This study aims to fill these gaps and provide a deeper understanding of the comparative performance of PS-InSAR and NSBAS methodologies in land subsidence analysis.

This study employs Monte-Carlo sampling to select the area of interest (AOI) in North Jakarta. It estimates the deviation of velocity (mm/year) produced by the SAR algorithm within a 0.5 km x 0.5 km grid using spatially weighted averages (SWA). For validation and ground-check purposes, land subsidence measurements were obtained in collaboration with Balai Konservasi Air Tanah (BKAT), which has monitored subsidence through Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) measurements in the Greater Jakarta Area since the early 1990s. The findings presented in this study are further supported by multiple publications and reports frequently highlighted in both national and international media (Abidin et al., 2015; Bott et al., 2021; Ng et al., 2012; Widodo et al., 2019, 2022). This study incorporates SAR analysis using PS-InSAR and NSBAS methodologies alongside a statistical approach utilizing SWA. Several assumptions were established before analysis, particularly concerning area coverage, coherence points, and building density. To minimize data bias, this study's visualization and statistical analysis focus on a relatively small region of North Jakarta. Subsidence levels in the AOI are categorized into high-rate, mid-rate, and low-rate subsidence. These classifications are based on observations from PS-InSAR results, field sampling, and prior geotechnical and geodetic research (Abidin et al., 2008; Marwanza et al., 2023).

The interferogram unwrapping process, phase looping, coherence assessment, and inversion are critical steps significantly contributing to variations in SAR processing outcomes. PS-InSAR method utilizes multiple scenes of Sentinel-1A data, characterized by a 250 km swath, a spatial resolution of 5 m by 20 m (single look), and C-band frequency, making it highly effective for detecting land subsidence and deformation in urban areas. Additionally, Sentinel-1A data in Single Look Complex (SLC) format can be accessed free of charge via the Alaska Satellite Facility (ASF) archives (Potin et al., 2016). The findings of this study highlight the reliability of PS-InSAR, demonstrating that its outcomes depend largely on specific research objectives and methodological considerations. When discrepancies between results are minimal, researchers are encouraged to prioritize computational efficiency, optimizing computational resources and processing time. This research addresses a gap in the existing literature, where previous studies primarily focused on comparisons of processing approaches for DInSAR, without applying statistical approaches to analyze their outputs (Elisabeth & Jean-Michel, 2012). This study analyzes differences in modular steps and empirical equations between the PS-InSAR and NSBAS methods.

1.1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Detection of ground deformation on topographical surfaces is achievable using spaceborne radar imagery, with detection accuracy reaching the centimeter scale, making it suitable for large-scale investigations. This technique is called Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (InSAR) (Perissin, 2016). Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) technology operates by transmitting electromagnetic signals

to the Earth's surface and analyzing the backscattered signals received by the satellite, as illustrated in Figure 1.1. InSAR has been widely utilized across various fields, including civil infrastructure monitoring (Shouhei et al., 2021), coastal mapping (Suroso & Firman, 2018), agriculture (Manago et al., 2020), deforestation (Masolele et al., 2021) and military applications (Z. Luo et al., 2019). Despite its versatility and numerous advantages, SAR imaging faces limitations, particularly speckle noise in the radar data (Baraha & Sahoo, 2023). Speckle noise reduces image quality and introduces distortions in the data, hindering accurate analysis. To mitigate speckle noise, researchers have developed various techniques, such as employing singular value decomposition (SVD) models (Baraha & Sahoo, 2023; Ren et al., 2015) and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) temporal filtering (Kustiyo et al., 2021). As SAR data processing and filtering algorithms continue to evolve, further efforts can be directed towards enhancing these methods by incorporating insights into the statistical behavior of SAR imagery and optimizing data analysis techniques.

Figure 1.1 Illustration of EM angular propagation, scattering, and satellite imaging geometry for SAR (Modified from Baraha & Sahoo, 2023).

1.2. PS-InSAR

InSAR processing using the Persistent Scatterer (PS) method involves co-registration steps in which the offset distribution of ground scatterers is cross-correlated. High-quality data is indicated by minimal discrepancies between multiple radar images (Z. Chen et al., 2016). Co-registration is essential for ensuring dataset accuracy and establishing a temporal baseline. Previous studies have used SARPROZ tool program as a PS processing tool (Kumar et al., 2020; Perissin et al., 2011; Widodo et al., 2022). The program is developed by Daniel Perissin (Perissin, 2022; Perissin et al., 2011), is based on MATLAB source code and has been continuously refined since its introduction in 2009. This application program is recognized as a reliable tool for SAR processing, utilized not only by academic institutions but also by companies and government organizations worldwide requiring satellite-based radar analysis. SARPROZ is available in two versions: a compiled version for independent use by general users and a P-code version that must be executed within MATLAB (Bokhari et al., 2023). Although MATLAB can be installed on Linux systems, Linux users rarely use it as standalone software due to the availability of alternative open-source programs (Abu Talib, 2016). While SARPROZ offers comprehensive processing capabilities and detailed analytical tools, its computational and time-processing demands are significant, particularly when handling large datasets comprising multiple radar images. As a commercial software, SARPROZ requires a valid license, and its source code is inaccessible for customization or modification. This limitation restricts the ability of researchers or third parties to adapt or extend the software for specific needs, effectively

positioning it as a closed ecosystem. While this structure ensures software integrity and security, it may pose challenges for users seeking flexible or open-source alternatives to tailor the software for advanced or unconventional applications. The PS method, which relies on a multi-temporal interferometric dataset, requires an initial interferogram designated as the master, with subsequent interferograms treated as slaves. The PS analysis process generates a reflectivity map, a valuable module for comparing scattering intensities across radar images (Perissin et al., 2016). Additionally, the interferogram unwrapping algorithm used in PS differs from that applied in SBAS, enabling distinct processing approaches for these two methods. It can be written as:

$$\phi_{i,k}^{UW}(s,l) = \phi_{i,k}(s,l) \pm 2\pi n \quad (1)$$

Where n is the integer number, ϕ is the interferogram wrapped phase, (s,l) is the image coordinates in the images normalized complex cross-correlation coefficient i,k . That equation denotes the complex number calculation to produce a coherence point. If the interferogram produces poor coherence, adding other multiple interferograms might increase the results (Perissin et al., 2016). Since the PS resolves time series deformation mapping by characterizing the anomaly driven by backscattering and atmospheric delay, it becomes more stable over time. It does not show temporal decorrelation, enabling long-term observation and tracking of any deformation (J. Khan et al., 2022). Before moving forward from an interferogram to the fundamental step for PS-InSAR, users must remember that the interferogram comprises several types of information. In simple terms, it can be written as (Jácome et al., 2020; Welikanna et al., 2021):

$$\phi_{i,k}^W = \phi_{topography} + \phi_{atmosphere} + \phi_{orbit} + \phi_{movement} + \phi_{noise} \quad (2)$$

Several factors influence variations in interferometric phases, each corresponding to specific physical or operational conditions. For instance, topographic height errors, particularly in mountainous regions, contribute to phase variations ($\phi_{topography}$). Similarly, atmospheric delays ($\phi_{atmosphere}$) introduce distortions in the wrapped interferogram due to changes in atmospheric conditions. Noise-related phase errors (ϕ_{noise}), including their derivatives, are often caused by radar signal attenuation, which may originate from thermal noise or hardware component errors.

Orbital phase shifts (ϕ_{orbit}), resulting from satellite trajectory deviations, also contribute to phase variations and require correction through preprocessing. Additionally, phase variations due to satellite movement acceleration ($\phi_{movement}$) are directly related to the Line of Sight (LOS) path, which represents the radar signal's propagation direction. For further details on LOS, readers may refer to relevant publications (Hu et al., 2019; M. A. Khan et al., 2019; X. Luo et al., 2020). Furthermore, a complex form of interferogram can be written Φ associated with the differences between two or more SAR images with distinct phases(ϕ) and complex signal (Π); it can be written as follows (Bokhari et al., 2023; X. Chen et al., 2021):

$$\Phi = \Pi_m \Pi_{s+i} = A_m A_{s+i} e^{j\Delta\phi} \quad (3)$$

where,

$$\Pi = \begin{cases} \Pi_m = A_m \phi_m \\ \Pi_s = \sum_0^i A_{s+i} \phi_{s+i} \end{cases}, \text{with } i = \text{integers} \quad (4)$$

$$\phi = \phi_m - \phi_s = 4\pi\Delta R\lambda^{-1} \quad (5)$$

Note that the amplitude (A) is part of a complex signal caused by electromagnetic waves emitted by space satellites. Since the discrepancy from two or more SAR images ($e^{j\Delta\phi}$) is calculated during interferogram construction, and the co-registration for generating the temporal baseline distribution can be determined. PS-InSAR generally demonstrates its superiority against DInSAR but requires more computational resources. Further research about DInSAR for land subsidence and geological

approach can be read in this publication (Bozzan et al., 2015). The atmospheric phase screen removal (APS) is a part of the following processing steps for PS-InSAR. The equation for the atmospheric phase screen can be written as (Jung et al., 2014):

$$\phi_{APS} = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} [L_d^s - \quad (6)$$

Due to atmospheric delay L_d between master and slave, SAR images have differences and each ϕ_{APS} is associated with hydrostatic delay (L_d^{Hydro}), ionosphere delay (L_d^{Ion}), wet delay (L_d^{wet}) and liquid delay (L_d^{liq}). However, runny and wet delays only contribute to a small portion and, therefore, can be ignored as the major component of interferogram distortion. Hence, the empirical equation can be denoted below (Jung et al., 2014):

$$L_d = L_d^{Ion} + L_d^{Hydro} + L_d^{wet} + L_d^{liq} \quad (7)$$

Therefore,

$$\Delta L_d \approx \Delta L_d^{Hydro} + \Delta L_d^{wet} \quad (8)$$

Since the APS process must refer to the Permanent Scatterers Candidate (PSC), which means they pass thoroughly the Amplitude stability Index (ASI), every pixel that consistently has equivalent amplitude overall data collection is expected to have small phase dispersion (PD). In relevant to that, the equation of ASI can be written as (Fárová et al., 2019):

$$ASI = 1 - D_A = 1 - (\sigma_A / \delta_A) \quad (9)$$

Where D_A is a symbol for amplitude dispersion that can be equal to the standard deviation of amplitude in time σ_A divided by the mean deviation of amplitude in time δ_A . In SARPROZ tool program, all equations are embedded in the GUI and can be selected by choosing options inside the pop-up windows, as illustrated in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2. Interface with various options for Persistent Scatterer (PS) processing

1.3. NSBAS

A brief history of SBAS and its development are explained clearly by Li et al. in their publication (Li et al., 2022). The authors intend to highlight some important information as a basis for this study and simultaneously give a message to the readers that InSAR technology continues growing and becoming better in satellite resolution and processing algorithms. Initially, the earlier development

method to process InSAR data was the DInSAR method, which combined different radar interferograms to extract elevation information from the ground surface by calculating the phase difference of ($\Delta\phi$) of two SAR images (Gabriel et al., 1989). Subsequently, it was found that atmospheric effects and spatio-temporal decorrelation had noise, which affected the results. The atmospheric conditions caused errors and created a bias in signal propagation emitted by the satellite. Further developments discovered that deviation of amplitude within a pixel image at a specific range gives better phase stability and strengthens the data. This pixel was invoked as a permanent scatterer, which led to the new development of the InSAR method known as PS-InSAR (Ferretti et al., 2000, 2001). On the other hand, other researchers developed a different approach called the small spatio-temporal baseline, which later became known as SBAS (Usai, 2001, 2002). The principle of traditional SBAS is using the least-square method to retrieve time-series deformation. However, the shortcoming of SBAS is the rank deficit problems that occur during least-square calculation, which was later solved by singular value decomposition (SVD) (Berardino et al., 2002). The empirical equation for traditional SBAS can be expressed as follows (Doin et al., 2011; Li et al., 2022):

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{t_1}^{UW}(x, r) &= \phi_{t_2}(x, r) - \phi_{t_1}(x, r) \\ &\approx \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} (z(t_2, x, r) - z(t_1, x, r)) + \Delta\phi_{topography}^i + \Delta\phi_{noise}^i \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Where (x,r) is high coherence point, $z(t_2, x, r) - z(t_1, x, r)$ is the cumulative displacement of LOS, while t_2 and t_1 indices time range, subsequently $\Delta\phi_{topography}^i$ is topography residual errors from DEM and $\Delta\phi_{noise}^i$ is APS and other errors. There are plenty of SBAS derivatives since it was first used to monitor ground deformation, although, in this study, NSBAS was selected and applied in our analysis. The illustration of the SBAS development timeline as part of the SAR method can be seen in Figure 1.3; further reading is in Li et al., 2022 publication.

Figure 1.3. Timeline of SAR development (modified from Li et al., 2022)

In this study, the authors employed LiCSBAS, made by Yu Morishita (Morishita, 2021; Morishita et al., 2020), which implements NSBAS concepts and focuses on Python source code that is easy to reproduce or develop, even though the creator has stated he left it to the end user to use his

software at his own risk, the cloud server that he made is still running and continuously providing interferogram data set since 2015. Unlike SARPROZ, which runs everything from the start, LiCSBAS does not need to create an interferogram as it is already predefined in a cloud server, and the unwrapping process becomes more manageable. However, since a basic understanding of Python and Linux is mandatory for LiCSBAS users, working on a black-and-white screen like a terminal ecosystem is often necessary during the processing work. There is not much optional selection input unless declared in the manual instructions. For advanced users of LiCSBAS, modifications can be made to the algorithms that can be adjusted to their needs. For the best experience using LiCSBAS, it is suggested that the user should read the manual instructions. The phase unwrapping imageries are provided routinely through a cloud system facilitated by the Center for Observation and Modelling of Earthquakes, Volcanoes, and Tectonics (COMET) and can be downloaded at no cost. The first step for LiCSBAS, as referred to in the instructions, is selecting the Area of Interest (AOI) and choosing the mosaic frame ID polygon from the COMET-LiCS web.

Therefore, this study does not cover how phase unwrapping interferograms are constructed in LiCSBAS. Still, for readers who want to explore more about arranged algorithms, some publications can help give a detailed illustration (C. W. Chen & Zebker, 2002; Lazecky et al., 2022; Morishita, 2022). As stated in prior steps, after selecting the AOI, the users are directed to automatically check the cut version of the phase unwrapping interferogram, since it is invoked as a quality check that separates the bad and good quality of the data. The insufficient data is described as a decorrelated interferogram caused by vegetation canopy, incomplete mosaic data, or snow cover. Moreover, the insufficient data demonstrates the low percentages of valid unwrapped pixels (Morishita et al., 2020). Once the quality check is completed and high-quality data is identified, LiCSBAS users can proceed to the Loop Closure Process (LCP) step. This step integrates the Small Baseline Subset (SBAS) network, applying corrections to errors introduced during phase unwrapping. Unlike pixel-by-pixel analysis, this refinement process operates on an image-by-image basis, improving the overall consistency of the dataset. This methodology ensures that unwrapping errors are systematically minimized, providing a robust foundation for subsequent processing steps in SAR-based analyses. The equation for loop closure, as stated by the creator of LiCSBAS, can be mathematically expressed as follows:

$$\phi_{123} = \phi_{12} + \phi_{23} - \phi_{13} \quad (9)$$

If the phase unwrapping errors exist in the dataset, they will be removed during the LCP steps by selecting the smallest root mean square (RMS) value. Technical explanations about erroneous cancellation and removal can be seen in (Morishita et al., 2020) publication. The next step is Small Base Inversion (SBI), where the small baseline interferogram will be inverted to achieve a time series of velocity and surface displacement. Further process of the LiCSBAS processing can be seen in the method section in this article. The image captured from the LiCSBAS interface in the Ubuntu terminal is denoted in Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4. LiCSBAS installation check in Linux (Ubuntu 20.04) command prompt.

The LiCSBAS uses the pre-defined interferograms produced with pixel resolution 10-3 x 10-3 degrees or ~100 x 100 m for the record. It is part of the LiCSAR (Looking into Continents from Space with Synthetic Aperture Radar) project and uses Sentinel 1A based on the dataset (Al Ghiffari et al., 2022). The last step from SBAS in LiCSBAS software is Spatiotemporal Filtering of Time Series. This Gaussian filtering is conducted to remove troposphere and ionosphere noise from the inversion SBAS-masking data. Global scientists commonly use LiCSBAS software to solve their monitoring and investigation of natural disasters related to land deformation and its relatives (Al Ghiffari et al., 2022; Hayati et al., 2022; Morishita, 2022).

1.4. General Comparison of Both Methods

In more detail, the algorithms of the PS-InSAR and NSBAS methods have been explained in various manual publications, which serve as references for this study as fundamental approaches. The NSBAS method, which is based on open-source principles, offers greater flexibility, particularly because it uses Python-based source code, allowing for modifications to meet specific needs. On the other hand, the PS-InSAR method, designed for specific operating system ecosystems, provides advantages in ease of use with an intuitive interface that supports efficient management of Sentinel-1A datasets. The compatibility of these methods with other spatial and image analysis tools, such as GIS, further accelerates data analysis and ensures the delivery of desirable outputs. The PS-InSAR method is often developed using specific programming languages and can operate without requiring a full license for additional software, relying instead on relevant runtime environments. This study compares the results obtained from the PS-InSAR and NSBAS methods to provide a comprehensive perspective. The aim of this comparison is to help readers understand the strengths and limitations of each method, enabling them to select the most suitable one for their specific research needs. In general, the strengths and weaknesses of both methods can be identified separately, as presented in Table 1.1. Although the algorithms used in PS-InSAR and NSBAS differ, both share the same goal: to develop monitoring systems and investigate land deformation and changes. Various previous studies and publications have demonstrated the advantages of each method in supporting land deformation monitoring research.

Table 1.1. The different aspects between PS-InSAR and NSBAS methods.

Descriptions	PS-InSAR	NSBAS
Based code	MATLAB	Python
Number of Processing Steps	≥10	6

Descriptions	PS-InSAR	NSBAS
(refers to manual instruction)		
SLC data	Required	Not Required
Interferogram	Generate manually	Predefined
GUI	Window Based	Text-based/Command Prompt
Open Source	No-under company license	Yes, free to use
Hardware Requirements	Mid-High Hardware specification	Low-Mid Hardware specification
Data Format	Multi-Format	GeoTiff
Resolution of the data	depends on the satellite data input	Sentinel 1A
Libraries requirements	complex	simply
Internet dependency	During processing the data	During downloading the data
Common Output Format	Point (csv, kmz, shp)	Point (HDF5, txt)
Computational Time (Relatively)	Intermediate – long (Depends on the number of images)	Rapid – Intermediate (depends on the range of observation time)

2. METHOD AND SCOPE OF STUDY

2.1. Study Area

This research employs forward modeling where data from Sentinel-1A are processed using NSBAS and PS-InSAR. The results are later compared to see which one resembles actual conditions. Then, a mathematical approach is used to obtain details corresponding to historical land subsidence in the areas of interest. Due to the limitations of our computational hardware, in this study, samples were taken from several areas inside the North Jakarta Administrative (NJA), where they were selected based on the existing monitoring GNSS installed. Nonetheless, the authors also generated some selected observation areas with a Monte-Carlo for comparison. The NJA was used as a case study to evaluate how significant the methods and its tools are to confirm land subsidence in coastal-urban areas. This area has been studied for many years by governments and scientists worldwide (Abidin et al., 2008; Bott et al., 2021; Putri et al., 2013; Sumantyo et al., 2016). There have been plenty of research articles and news reports about this area. In Figure 2.1, the area close to the coastline can be seen. Thus, seawater intrusion is assumed to be associated with reduced groundwater volume at the study site.

Figure 2.1. AOI in this study, North Jakarta Administrative

Subsequently, the geology of the study area (see Figure 2.2) consists of Quaternary sediment, which aggregates from sand, gravel, pebbles, boulders, clay, and silt. Most of these are formed from

alluvium deposits laid down in layers through a stratigraphic process. Since this study examines both methods in this area, the authors focus on evaluating the accuracy of implementation between the PS-InSAR and NSBAS methods rather than discussing the causes of subsidence. Readers are encouraged to refer to other publications for detailed studies related to land subsidence in this area (Abidin et al., 2015; Ng et al., 2012; Putri et al., 2013).

Figure 2.2. Geology map of the study area (source: Indonesia MNRE, 1991)

2.2. Method

This study compares the performance of Persistent Scatterer InSAR (PS-InSAR) and New Small Baseline Subset (NSBAS) algorithms in detecting and analyzing land subsidence. These algorithms operate on different platforms—PS-InSAR is processed on Windows 10, while NSBAS runs on Ubuntu 20.04 Linux, which may present advantages and limitations depending on system compatibility and computational efficiency. While previous studies have primarily focused on estimating annual subsidence rates, many lack a thorough evaluation of the confidence levels in their measurements and the impact of computational variations. Given that different InSAR algorithms cater to specific research needs, the terrain type, data availability, and computational requirements often drive the choice of method.

The North Jakarta Administrative (NJA) area was selected as the study site due to its well-documented history of land subsidence, providing an ideal case for comparative analysis. The primary dataset used is Sentinel-1A, which, despite its spatial resolution limitations, offers free accessibility, enabling efficient and large-scale processing. However, the study does not investigate the underlying causes of subsidence, such as excessive groundwater extraction, coastal dynamics, or infrastructural loads. Instead, the focus remains on evaluating the performance, reliability, and computational efficiency of PS-InSAR and NSBAS for large-scale land deformation monitoring.

2.2.1. PS-InSAR Processing

The PS-InSAR processing workflow (Figure 2.3) consists of a systematic sequence of steps to accurately analyze ground deformation from radar imagery. The process begins with data preparation, where Single Look Complex (SLC) data are imported, orbital corrections are applied,

master and slave images are selected, and ground control points (GCP) along with a digital elevation model (DEM) are used for coregistration. In the prelude analysis phase, essential parameters such as reflectivity maps and amplitude stability indices are computed, followed by the selection of Persistent Scatterer (PS) candidates and the removal of the amplitude-phase screen (APS). The InSAR processing stage involves setting processing parameters, estimating coherence, generating interferograms, and producing coherence maps, culminating in deformation calculations. The final phase, map preparation, includes geocoding, visualization, overlaying results on platforms like Google Earth, map editing, and creating the final deformation map. This workflow ensures a scientifically robust approach for detecting and analyzing land deformation.

Figure 2.3. The PS-InSAR Workflow (Modified from Bokhari et al., 2023; Kumar et al., 2020; Widodo et al.,2022)

2.2.2. NSBAS Processing

The workflow for NSBAS processing (Figure 2.4) involves a systematic approach to data correction, filtering, and time-series analysis, as outlined in the manual by Morishita et al. (Morishita et al., 2020). The process begins with data preparation, where unwrapped phase (UNW) and coherence (COH) GeoTIFF files are loaded. In the prelude analysis phase, the time period of interest is selected, and unwrapped GeoTIFF imagery is downloaded and downsampled. Quality checks are performed to ensure data reliability, with optional corrections such as GACOS (Global Atmospheric Correction Online Service) for masking unwrapped phases and dipping data in accordance with the area of interest (AOI). Following the prelude analysis, SBAS processing involves time-series analysis, starting with loop closure and noise separation to identify reliable unwrapped data (UNW). Good UNW data are subjected to small baseline inversion, resulting in a time series of deformation. The velocity of deformation is calculated, and its standard deviation (STD) is determined using bootstrap analysis. Filtering and deramping are then applied to refine the time series. Finally, the results are displayed, providing insights into deformation trends over the selected period. This workflow integrates quality assurance steps and advanced correction modules, ensuring accurate and reliable deformation analysis.

Figure 2.4. NSBAS Workflow (Modified Morishita, 2021; Morishita et al., 2020)

2.3. Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis in this study was designed to evaluate and compare the performance of the PS-InSAR and NSBAS algorithms in detecting and measuring land subsidence. The methodology involved data preparation, random sampling, and statistical analysis, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of both methods. The results were presented using histograms, radar graphs, and tables to illustrate deviations, variances, and accuracy levels effectively.

2.3.1. Data Preparation and Random Sampling

The analysis commenced with the preparation of datasets obtained from PS-InSAR and NSBAS outputs. The PS-InSAR results were provided in spatial point format, whereas NSBAS results were in raster format. To ensure an unbiased spatial representation, a Monte Carlo sampling method was applied to generate random sampling points within the Area of Interest (AOI). These points served as the basis for statistical comparison and analysis of subsidence rates derived from both methods.

The Monte Carlo method is a widely used statistical technique that relies on the random generation of sample points based on uniform probability distributions. In this study, the random spatial coordinates (X_i, Y_i) within the AOI were generated using the following formula:

$$X_i = X_{\min} + (X_{\max} - X_{\min}) \times U(0,1) \quad (10)$$

$$Y_i = Y_{\min} + (Y_{\max} - Y_{\min}) \times U(0,1) \quad (11)$$

where:

X_i, Y_i = randomly generated coordinates within the AOI

X_{\min}, X_{\max} = minimum and maximum X-coordinates of the AOI

Y_{\min}, Y_{\max} = minimum and maximum Y-coordinates of the AOI

$U(0,1)$ = a uniformly distributed random number between 0 and 1

This method ensures that sampling points are evenly distributed within the AOI, preventing biases in the dataset selection. The land subsidence monitoring data used for validation were obtained from the Balai Konservasi Air Tanah (BKAT) and stored in .xlsx format. These datasets were processed using the R programming environment, leveraging advanced spatial analysis libraries such as raster, sf, terra, and rgeos. The PS-InSAR point data were converted into spatial data frames, while NSBAS data were maintained in their original raster format. To refine the spatial analysis, buffer zones were created around the random sampling points to incorporate all relevant data within a

defined proximity. This buffering technique ensured that subsidence values from both PS-InSAR and NSBAS were included in the comparative analysis, allowing for a more precise assessment of their accuracy and consistency. By integrating the Monte Carlo sampling method with spatial data processing techniques in R, this study ensured a robust and statistically reliable framework for comparing PS-InSAR and NSBAS results in land subsidence monitoring.

2.3.2. Statistical Comparison and Analysis

The statistical analysis involved calculating the deviation in subsidence rates (mm/year) between PS-InSAR, NSBAS, and ground truth data at each sampling location to evaluate the accuracy of both methods. Variance and standard deviation (STD) were computed to assess the consistency and reliability of the subsidence rates produced by each algorithm. Additionally, buffer zones were applied to incorporate all relevant data within a defined area, enabling a consistent comparison between the sparse spatial point data of PS-InSAR and the raster format of NSBAS. A correlation analysis was then performed to determine the level of agreement between the two methods, assessing how closely their results aligned in terms of subsidence patterns and rates.

Two key metrics were calculated to further evaluate accuracy. The average deviation quantified the mean difference in subsidence rates (mm/year) between PS-InSAR and NSBAS across all sampling locations. Additionally, the accuracy percentage measured the proportion of results within an acceptable deviation threshold (e.g., less than 20%), highlighting how closely each method's results aligned with ground truth data. This combined analysis provided a comprehensive assessment of the performance and reliability of both methods.

3. RESULT

3.1. PS-InSAR Processing Results

PS-InSAR processing steps did not require advanced coding execution skills, and GUI windows can select options. Even though, in the background, several instructions operate in the command window. The interferogram was stacked from SLC based on the 2021 to 2022 period and using SENTINEL-1A data with 24 images. The master image and slave were chosen as the next step, and the SLC from 8 January 2021 was used as the master image. Subsequently, the co-registration process was performed to generate temporal coherence and a multi-image interferogram. The results can be seen in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1. Coherence and unwrapping phase of SAR Interferometry generated from PS-InSAR for the Jakarta area.

As illustrated in previous workflows, the displacement of the Area of Interest (AOI) can be represented using a frequency histogram (see Figure 3.2.). This allows for a clear statistical interpretation of subsidence patterns through a structured analysis. In this study, the PS-InSAR interferogram baseline plot could not be displayed due to technical errors in the operating system.

Figure 3.2. The displacement histogram obtained from the analysis illustrates the distribution of suspected subsidence locations

The final map consists of two main objects. The first is a base map acquired from the Google Earth optical database, which presents information about the AOI, such as roads, buildings, space areas, and more. The second is a sparse point PS generated from multi-interferometric image processing with coordinates and displacement velocities in time series for the observed location. This final map becomes the input for further statistical analysis, where each "sparse point" is used as a variable to perform difference calculations and correlations with other adjacent variables. The actual measurements or monitoring GNSS are marked as square shapes on the final map, while the "sparse points" from PS-InSAR are plotted as circular dots with graduated colors (see Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4. The final PS-InSAR map for the AOI was generated using interferometric processing

In Figure 3.4, subsidence occurred in almost all locations within the AOI according to the PS-InSAR processing. It is most prominent in the northern area of NJA, where the coastline interacts with seawater. Seawater intrusion may have influenced this area over an extended period. A key aspect of this study is that PS-InSAR provides a high density of subsidence points, enabling analysis in areas where direct measurements were not feasible. However, processing 24 images of PS-InSAR required a significant amount of time.

3.2. NSBAS Processing Results

NSBAS enables users to perform InSAR analysis with basic command-line operations, making it accessible for systems with low hardware specifications. However, processing time may depend on internet speed, particularly for certain input data. In this study, the results for the DJA case were obtained using NSBAS, and the unwrapped phase can be observed in Figure 3.5. The figure illustrates areas with missing pixels and phase changes reflecting SAR scattering effects. Further analysis of the small baseline network for this AOI from 2021 to 2022 revealed significant phase variations, indicating substantial ground displacement over time.

Figure 3.5. The images of the unwrapping phase (the rectangular boundary is NJA).

The small baseline network can be seen in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6. The network graph from the interferogram is based on the temporal baseline - NSBAS collected from 2021 to 2022.

As mentioned in the previous section, the loop closure process provides information regarding insufficient data and errors, and they were removed during this process to refine the unwrapped phases interferogram; hence, they will be needed for the following processing steps (see Figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7. The loop closure process in NSBAS generates the RMS and corrects errors in the interferogram unwrapping phase, enhancing the accuracy of the final displacement results

Further processing after loop closure was performed is a Small Baseline Inversion and velocity calculation, and the results are illustrated in Figure 3.8.a. Subsequently, the mask and filtering time series were implemented on the previously output data. An illustration of this process can be seen in Figure 3.9.

Figure 3.8. The Small Baseline Inversion and velocity calculation results

Figure 3.9. Filter results obtained from NSBAS processing

Figure 3.10. illustrates the timeline of historical subsidence in the AOI, indicating that subsidence gradually occurred annually. What is essential is that the time-series graph provides information about average subsidence velocity.

Figure 3.10. Result from NSBAS processing (sample point) in the AOI to illustrate the cumulative displacement in the time series.

The output from NSBAS is in 'hdf5' format, which, like raster data, can be converted into GeoTIFF using specific algorithms. The hdf5 file contains spatial data in Cartesian coordinates. The raster data derived from NSBAS is processed using the 'terra' package in R, enabling the extraction and analysis of land subsidence velocity (in mm/year). This information is then compared statistically with actual field measurements to assess accuracy and reliability (see Figure 3.11).

Figure 3.11. The final map from NSBAS in AOI

3.3. Random Sampling for Comparison

A typical approach to estimating the difference between two or more data series was to calculate the deviation. The simple reason is to illustrate how accurate the generated data is to the actual conditions. Furthermore, mathematical theory was implemented as part of the analysis. The Monte-Carlo method generated random sampling locations for the analysis requirement. The data on land subsidence monitoring were obtained from BKAT and stored in *.xlsx format. Since the statistical analysis was more straightforward to conduct in statistical software, R-code was selected as the basis for performing the computational statistics. The raster and spatial point can be read and loaded into the R global environment, and both can be viewed after being stored using R-Studio. R has powerful Python-like libraries and can be installed by providing input commands to the console window. Libraries such as "raster," "sf," "terra," and "rgeos" are used and assigned to datasets. A simple workflow to demonstrate the process can be illustrated as follows (see Figure 3.12).

Figure 3.12. Workflow of the statistical analysis for comparing PS-InSAR and NSBAS

Since PS-InSAR and NSBAS produce different data types, a conversion process was required for comparative analysis. The sparse point data from PS-InSAR were transformed into a spatial point data frame using the "rgeos" package, while the NSBAS raster data were retained in their original format. Buffer zones were generated to define the boundary areas, ensuring that all datasets within these zones were incorporated into the analysis. Subsequently, statistical analysis was conducted to quantify discrepancies and assess the statistical properties of both datasets. Finally, the accuracy percentage of each method was calculated to evaluate its reliability in measuring land subsidence.

The sampling methodology utilized in this study is illustrated as follows (see Figure 3.13).

Figure 3.13. Sample scenarios for the outputs of both methods, where the buffer area acts as a boundary for data sampling.

3.4. Correlation Analysis Between NSBAS and PS-InSAR

The correlation between both methods and their respective outputs has been analyzed, demonstrating the consistency of the calculations in producing comparable results. However, significant discrepancies are observed within specific ranges, as presented in Figure 3.14.

Figure 3.14. Sample statistical comparison of PS-InSAR and NSBAS results

The statistical comparison of PS-InSAR and NSBAS results provides critical insight into the significance of selecting appropriate methods for accurate land subsidence analysis. Table 3.1 presents the discrepancies between observed ground truth data and SAR-derived measurements.

Table 3.1 Statistical comparison of PS-InSAR, NSBAS, and ground truth monitoring.

Sampling Locations	STD group (σ)	Variance (σ^2)	Mean ($mm/year$) PS-InSAR	Mean ($mm/year$) NSBAS	Monitoring Well	Δd
Ancol Baru	4.67	21.8	-4.99	-0.44	-1.18	4.55
Kebon Bawang	4.32	18.74	-9.78	-7.17	-0.82	2.61
Kemayoran	2.98	8.9	-2.87	2.02	0.00	4.89
Koja	4.17	17.46	-9.35	-2.95	Not observed	6.4
Muara Angke	6.96	48.57	-26.4	-29.31	-3.12	2.83
Muara Baru	7.01	49.27	-19.66	19.52	-4.25	39.19
Pademangan Timur	3.25	10.59	-3.82	0.10	Not observed	3.92
Pantai Indah Kapuk (PIK)	3.49	12.24	-4.55	-11.50	-1.74	6.94
Pluit	2.05	4.23	-0.25	-3.06	-3.90	2.81
Rawa Badak	1.75	3.06	-1.69	-2.48	Not observed	0.78
Sunter	2.07	4.28	-0.31	4.54	-0.64	4.85
Tongkol	2.36	5.57	-1.05	-0.32	-3.78	0.73

The analysis revealed that the deviation between PS-InSAR and NSBAS is approximately 2–4 mm/year, except for one outlier in Muara Baru, where the deviation exceeds 30 mm/year. This finding suggests that the differences in deviation results between PS-InSAR and NSBAS are not statistically significant. However, the spatial coverage of PS-InSAR is denser compared to NSBAS, resulting in fewer data gaps, as indicated by the calculations in Table 3.2. While PS-InSAR demonstrated slightly higher data quality than NSBAS, the overall difference remained minimal.

Table 3.2. Difference between actual conditions and SAR processing data.

	PS-InSAR	NSBAS	Δd	Description	Monitoring Well	$\Delta_{PSInSAR}$	Δ_{NSBAS}
1	-4.998	-0.443	4.555	Ancol Baru	-1.18	3.818	1.623
2	-9.787	-7.175	2.612	Kebon bawang	-0.82	8.967	7.995
3	-2.871	2.02	4.891	Kemayoran	0	2.871	2.02
4	-9.358	-2.958	6.4	Koja	Not observed	Not counted	Not counted
5	-26.48	-29.311	2.831	Muara Angke	-3.12	23.36	32.431
6	-19.669	19.522	39.191	Muara baru	-4.25	15.419	15.272

7	-3.828	0.101	3.929	Pademangan_Timur	Not observed	Not counted	Not counted
8	-4.557	-11.501	6.944	PIK	-1.74	2.817	13.241
9	-0.256	-3.066	2.81	Pluit	-3.9	3.644	6.966
10	-1.699	-2.485	0.786	Rawa Badak	Not observed	Not counted	Not counted
11	-0.314	4.54	4.854	Sunter	-0.64	0.326	3.9
12	-1.057	-0.323	0.734	Tongkol	-3.78	2.723	4.103
Average Deviation						7.105	9.727

Table 3.2. presents the statistical comparison between the results of PS-InSAR and NSBAS analyses in relation to ground truth data. Deviations of less than 20% and accuracy levels exceeding 80% are considered acceptable for interpretation. Based on the analysis, the average deviations are approximately 7% for PS-InSAR and 9% for NSBAS. The corresponding accuracy levels are calculated to be around 93% for PS-InSAR and 90% for NSBAS. These findings indicate that both methods provide reliable results, with PS-InSAR demonstrating slightly higher accuracy and lower deviation. A visual representation of these variations is provided in Figure 3.16.

Figure 3.15. Histogram from Δd , which originates from the difference of mean

Figure 3.16. The radar graph comparing PS-InSAR and NSBAS indicates that PS-InSAR demonstrates higher accuracy

4. DISCUSSION

The selection of processing methodologies significantly impacts data processing efficiency, analysis accuracy, and usability. PS-InSAR processing offers a user-friendly interface with its GUI-based system, simplifying the processing workflow and making it accessible to users with limited coding expertise. However, its computational performance raises concerns, particularly when handling large datasets. For instance, processing 24 Sentinel-1A images required substantial time, reflecting scalability limitations. Conversely, NSBAS processing demonstrated lower computational demands and compatibility with modest hardware, enabling efficient processing. However, its reliance on internet connectivity for data acquisition and processing may limit its applicability in areas with poor network infrastructure.

The statistical analysis revealed comparable accuracy levels for PS-InSAR and NSBAS, with deviations ranging between 2–4 mm/year, except for an outlier in Muara Baru, where the deviation exceeded 30 mm/year. PS-InSAR achieved an accuracy of approximately 93%, while NSBAS attained 90%, both meeting acceptable thresholds for most subsidence studies. PS-InSAR's higher spatial density provided better resolution and minimized blank areas in displacement maps, making it more suitable for urban environments requiring high granularity. Conversely, NSBAS's raster-based approach is better suited for large-scale regional studies, offering moderate resolution with efficient processing (Ferretti et al., 2007; Morishita et al., 2020).

The computational demands for PS-InSAR were significantly higher than for NSBAS, as demonstrated by the hardware specifications used in this study (see Table 4). The workstation supporting PS-InSAR required 64 GB of RAM, an Intel Xeon Skylake processor, and 8 TB SSD storage, whereas the NSBAS setup operated with more modest specifications, including 32 GB of RAM and a mobile Intel i7 processor. While PS-InSAR benefits from its robust computational capabilities, the extended processing time for large datasets, such as the 24 Sentinel-1A images analyzed, poses scalability challenges. On the other hand, NSBAS's lower hardware requirements and faster processing make it more accessible, particularly for users with limited computational resources. However, its reliance on internet connectivity for data processing can limit its usability in areas with poor network infrastructure (Shimada, 2019; Morishita et al., 2020).

Table 4.1. General specifications of the hardware which is used for processing and analysis of PS-InSAR and NSBAS

Description	PS-InSAR	NSBAS
Processor	Workstation Intel Xeon Skylake (~3.9 GHz)	Mobile Workstation Intel I7 gen 4 (~3 Ghz)
Graphics Card	Nvidia Quadro RTX 4000 (8GB-192 bit)	Nvidia Quadro K4100M (2GB-128 bit)
Media Storage	8 TB SSD	1 TB SSD
LAN and data speed	Ethernet cable, 24-32 Mbps	Wireless connection, 4G/HSDPA
Random Access Memory (RAM)	64 GB	32 GB
Peripheral	Standard, extra cooling fan Workstation PC	standard
Estimation of power consumption	~1000 Watt	~125 Watt

The methodological differences between PS-InSAR and NSBAS are substantial. PS-InSAR's point-based analysis enables the generation of dense spatial point data with high accuracy, making it ideal for urban settings or areas with complex infrastructure where detailed monitoring is essential. Its structured and systematic processing workflow ensures consistency but is constrained by its

closed ecosystem, which limits external contributions and customization (Ferretti et al., 2011). In contrast, NSBAS's raster-based analysis is better suited for regional-scale studies, offering compatibility with open-source platforms. While its open-source nature fosters global collaboration and continuous algorithmic improvements, it lacks parameter control and customization, which can challenge less experienced users (Morishita et al., 2020; Al Ghiffari et al., 2022).

Integrating cloud-based unwrapping techniques has shown potential for significantly reducing processing time (Al Ghiffari et al., 2022; Morishita et al., 2021). However, this approach can introduce challenges, particularly for novice users who may lack expertise in adjusting critical parameters, leading to uncontrolled errors in interferogram processing. Balancing ease of use with the ability to fine-tune parameters is crucial for ensuring reliable results.

This study demonstrates the strengths and limitations of PS-InSAR and NSBAS, emphasizing the importance of selecting the appropriate method based on study objectives, resource availability, and the scale of analysis. PS-InSAR is highly suited for high-resolution applications in urban or infrastructure-disturbed areas, while NSBAS offers scalability and efficiency for regional-scale studies. Future research should focus on improving algorithmic efficiency, enhancing software adaptability, and integrating advanced processing techniques such as machine learning to reduce errors and improve performance.

In the future, this research will benefit society by enhancing the importance of integration between various SAR methods, such as PS-InSAR and NSBAS. Combining both methods with artificial intelligence can improve detection capabilities, reduce uncertainties, and develop sophisticated processing techniques. Additionally, integrating SAR-based methods with hydrological models and ground-based sensors may offer a deeper understanding of the factors contributing to land subsidence, particularly soil compaction and groundwater extraction in urban coastal environments. Finally, the development of SAR is not limited to processing techniques but also extends to data and sensors, such as C-band and L-band, where the combination of both satellite data is robust for detecting land change even in the presence of dense vegetation and infrastructure. This development significantly expands comparative studies across broader fields, from geological to climatic change.

5. CONCLUSION

Advances in InSAR techniques, such as PS-InSAR and SBAS, have effectively addressed limitations inherent in earlier methods like DInSAR, particularly in mitigating atmospheric delays and improving phase stability. In this study, PS-InSAR, as implemented in the processing workflow, demonstrated superior performance in the study area, producing denser spatial points and fewer blank areas compared to NSBAS. This characteristic makes PS-InSAR more suitable for high-precision subsidence monitoring, particularly in urban environments requiring detailed analysis.

The comparative analysis revealed that PS-InSAR exhibited greater consistency with field measurements, achieving an average deviation of approximately 7 mm/year, compared to 4 mm/year for NSBAS. While the difference in deviation was relatively minor, PS-InSAR's higher spatial resolution provided more comprehensive data coverage, making it advantageous for urban subsidence studies. Conversely, NSBAS demonstrated notable strengths in broader area coverage and faster processing times, particularly on systems with modest hardware specifications. However, limitations in NSBAS were evident, particularly in significant blank areas along the NJA coastline, which could impact its applicability in detailed urban studies.

This study emphasizes the necessity of aligning processing methods with the specific requirements of the research area. PS-InSAR is more effective for applications requiring high spatial resolution and precision, while NSBAS offers a practical solution for large-scale analyses, particularly in regions with limited computational resources. Both methods demonstrated acceptable

accuracy levels, with PS-InSAR achieving 93% accuracy and NSBAS achieving 90%, making them reliable options for land subsidence monitoring.

Continuous algorithm improvements are essential for advancing the accuracy, usability, and scalability of InSAR-based techniques. Future developments should focus on enhancing computational efficiency, reducing processing times, and integrating advanced technologies such as machine learning to address residual errors. Collaboration between developers and end-users ensures that InSAR tools remain adaptable to diverse geophysical challenges and deliver robust solutions for land subsidence studies.

Ethical Approval

Not Applicable

Availability of Supporting Data

The authors can confirm that all relevant data used in this study are included in the manuscript's article and/or information files entitled: "Comparative Analysis of PS-InSAR and NSBAS Methods for Land Subsidence Monitoring in Urban Coastal Areas". The data are available at request from the authors, and the available data can be accessed free of charge from the data source. The complete data availability statement can be found in the Appendix Data Availability Statement.

Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Author's Contributions

Nugraheni Setyaningrum and Galih Prasetya Dinanta contributed to the study conceptualization, methodology, data validation, and formal analysis. Rendi Handika, Awaluddin, Fiolenta Marpaung, Munawaroh, and Winarno performed data validation, formal analysis, and application programs comparison. Heri Sadmono, Andie Setyoko, and Aji Putra Perdana contributed to the supervision and final review of the manuscript. Nugraheni Setyaningrum and Galih Prasetya Dinanta wrote the first draft of the manuscript, and all authors commented on previous versions. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Appendix Data Availability Statement

Data	Source	Spatial resolution	Temporal Resolution	Reference
Monitoring GNSS	the Groundwater Conservation Center (BKAT)), Ministry of	Insitu data	2021 - 2022	-

	Energy and Mineral Resources (KESDM), Republic of Indonesia			
Sentinel 1 satellite imagery	European Union/ESA/Copernicus	It acquires data with a 250 km swath at 5 m by 20 m spatial resolution (single look)	2021 - 2022	https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/user-guides/sentinel-1-sar/

References

- Abidin, H. Z., Andreas, H., Djaja, R., Darmawan, D., & Gamal, M. (2008). Land subsidence characteristics of Jakarta between 1997 and 2005, as estimated using GPS surveys. *GPS Solutions*, 12(1), 23–32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10291-007-0061-0>
- Abidin, H. Z., Andreas, H., Gamal, J M, Gumilar, I., Napitupulu, M., Fukuda, Y., Deguchi, J T, Maruyama, J Y, & Riawan, J Edi. (2010). Land Subsidence Characteristics of the Jakarta Basin (Indonesia) and its Relationship with Groundwater Extraction and Sea Level Rise. In *Groundwater Response to Changing Climate* (Vol. 1). <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/edit/10.1201/b10530/groundwater-response-changing-climate-ian-holman-makoto-taniguchi?refId=da088c1b-91a7-450b-ba42-2b989f51018a&context=ubx>
- Abidin, H. Z., Andreas, H., Gumilar, I., & Brinkman, J. J. (2015). Study on the risk and impacts of land subsidence in Jakarta. *Proceedings of the International Association of Hydrological Sciences*, 372, 115–120. <https://doi.org/10.5194/piahs-372-115-2015>
- Abu Talib, M. (2016). Quality in Use Analysis to Evaluate User Experience of Open-Source Software Compatible with MATLAB. *International Journal of Open-Source Software and Processes*, 7(3), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJOSSP.2016070101>
- Al Ghiffari, M. R., Nugroho, D., Afifuddin, Agustan, A., Endyana, C., & Hendarmawan. (2022). Optimization of Loop Closure Phase on LiCSBAS for Ground Deformation Monitoring in Southern Sumatra. *2022 IEEE Asia-Pacific Conference on Geoscience, Electronics and Remote Sensing Technology (AGERS)*, 6–12. <https://doi.org/10.1109/AGERS56232.2022.10093536>
- Bagheri-Gavkosh, M., Hosseini, S. M., Ataie-Ashtiani, B., Sohani, Y., Ebrahimian, H., Morovat, F., & Ashrafi, S. (2021). Land subsidence: A global challenge. *Science of The Total Environment*, 778, 146193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.146193>

- Baraha, S., & Sahoo, A. K. (2023). Synthetic aperture radar image and its despeckling using variational methods: A Review of recent trends. *Signal Processing*, 212, 109156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sigpro.2023.109156>
- Berardino, P., Fornaro, G., Lanari, R., & Sansosti, E. (2002). A new algorithm for surface deformation monitoring based on small baseline differential SAR interferograms. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 40(11), 2375–2383. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2002.803792>
- Bokhari, R., Shu, H., Tariq, A., Al-Ansari, N., Guluzade, R., Chen, T., Jamil, A., & Aslam, M. (2023). Land subsidence analysis using synthetic aperture radar data. *Heliyon*, 9(3), e14690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e14690>
- Bott, L.-M., Schöne, T., Illigner, J., Haghshenas Haghghi, M., Gisevius, K., & Braun, B. (2021). Land subsidence in Jakarta and Semarang Bay – The relationship between physical processes, risk perception, and household adaptation. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 211, 105775. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2021.105775>
- Bozzano, F., Esposito, C., Franchi, S., Mazzanti, P., Perissin, D., Rocca, A., & Romano, E. (2015). Understanding the subsidence process of a quaternary plain by combining geological and hydrogeological modelling with satellite InSAR data: The Acque Albule Plain case study. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 168, 219–238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2015.07.010>
- Bui, L. K., Le, P. V. V., Dao, P. D., Long, N. Q., Pham, H. V., Tran, H. H., & Xie, L. (2021). Recent land deformation detected by Sentinel-1A InSAR data (2016–2020) over Hanoi, Vietnam, and the relationship with groundwater level change. *GIScience and Remote Sensing*, 58(2), 161–179. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15481603.2020.1868198>
- Chen, C. W., & Zebker, H. A. (2002). Phase unwrapping for large SAR interferograms: statistical segmentation and generalized network models. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 40(8), 1709–1719. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2002.802453>
- Chen, X., Tessari, G., Fabris, M., Achilli, V., & Floris, M. (2021). Comparison Between PS and SBAS InSAR Techniques in Monitoring Shallow Landslides. In N. Casagli, K. Sassa, & K. Takara (Eds.), *Understanding and Reducing Landslide Disaster Risk* (Vol. 3, pp. 155–161). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-60311-3_17
- Chen, Z., Zhang, L., & Zhang, G. (2016). An improved InSAR image co-registration method for pairs with relatively big distortions or large incoherent areas. *Sensors (Switzerland)*, 16(9). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s16091519>
- Cruz, H., Véstias, M., Monteiro, J., Neto, H., & Duarte, R. P. (2022). A Review of Synthetic-Aperture Radar Image Formation Algorithms and Implementations: A Computational Perspective. In *Remote Sensing* (Vol. 14, Issue 5). MDPI. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14051258>
- Doin, M.-P., Lodge, F., Guillaso, S., Jolivet, R., Lasserre, C., Ducret, G., Grandin, R., Pathier, E., & Pinel, V. (2011). Presentation of The Small Baseline Nsbas Processing Chain On A Case Example: The Etna Deformation Monitoring From 2003 To 2010 Using Envisat Data. *Fringe 2011 Workshop*. <http://www.openchannelsoftware.com/projects/ROI>
- Elisabeth, S., & Jean-Michel, F. (2012). An overview on interferometric SAR software and a comparison between DORIS and SARSCAPE packages. In *Geospatial Free and Open-Source Software in the 21st Century* (pp. 107–122).

- Fárová, K., Jelének, J., Kopačková-Strnadová, V., & Kycl, P. (2019). Comparing DInSAR and PSI techniques employed to Sentinel-1 data to monitor highway stability: A case study of a massive Dobkovičky landslide, Czech Republic. *Remote Sensing*, *11*(22). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11222670>
- Ferretti, A., Monti-Guarnieri, A., & Rocca, F. (2007). *Part C InSAR processing: a mathematical approach*.
- Ferretti, A., Prati, C., & Rocca, F. (2000). Nonlinear subsidence rate estimation using permanent scatterers in differential SAR interferometry. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, *38*(5), 2202–2212. <https://doi.org/10.1109/36.868878>
- Ferretti, A., Prati, C., & Rocca, F. (2001). Permanent scatterers in SAR interferometry. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, *39*(1), 8–20. <https://doi.org/10.1109/36.898661>
- Gabriel, A. K., Goldstein, R. M., & Zebker, H. A. (1989). Mapping small elevation changes over large areas: Differential radar interferometry. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *94*(B7), 9183. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JB094iB07p09183>
- Geology Agency-Ministry of Energy and Natural Resources. (2023). *Balai Konservasi Air Tanah*. <https://geologi.esdm.go.id/id/profil/tugas-fungsi/balai-konservasi-air-tanah> (accessed 2 July 2023)
- Gheorghe, M., & Armaş, I. (2016). Comparison of Multi-Temporal Differential Interferometry Techniques Applied to the Measurement of Bucharest City Subsidence. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, *32*, 221–229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proenv.2016.03.027>
- Golkar, A., Cataldo, G., & Osipova, K. (2021). Small satellite synthetic aperture radar (SAR) design: A trade space exploration model. *Acta Astronautica*, *187*, 458–474. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2021.07.009>
- Hayati, N., Widodo, A., Kurniawan, A., Sanjiwani, I. D. M. A., Darminto, M. R., Yudha, I. S., & Sumantyo, J. T. S. (2022). Small baselines techniques of time series InSAR to monitor and predict land subsidence causing flood vulnerability in Sidoarjo, Indonesia. *Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk*, *13*(1), 2124–2150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19475705.2022.2109518>
- Hu, B., Chen, J., & Zhang, X. (2019). Monitoring the Land Subsidence Area in a Coastal Urban Area with InSAR and GNSS. *Sensors*, *19*(14), 3181. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19143181>
- Jácome, M. C., Martínez-Graña, A. M., & Valdés, V. (2020). Detection of terrain deformations using InSAR techniques in relation to results on terrain subsidence (Ciudad de Zaruma, Ecuador). *Remote Sensing*, *12*(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12101598>
- Jung, J., Kim, D. J., & Park, S. E. (2014). Correction of atmospheric phase screen in time series InSAR using WRF model for monitoring volcanic activities. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, *52*(5), 2678–2689. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2013.2264532>
- Khan, J., Ren, X., Hussain, M. A., & Jan, M. Q. (2022). Monitoring Land Subsidence Using PS-InSAR Technique in Rawalpindi and Islamabad, Pakistan. *Remote Sensing*, *14*(15). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14153722>
- Khan, M. A., Vehmas, R., & Visa, A. (2019). Automatic detection of water inside concrete slabs using ground penetrating radar. *2019 IEEE Radar Conference, RadarConf 2019*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/RADAR.2019.8835797>

- Kumar, S., Kumar, D., Chaudhary, S. K., Singh, N., & Malik, K. K. (2020). Land subsidence mapping and monitoring using modified persistent scatterer interferometric synthetic aperture radar in Jharia Coalfield, India. *Journal of Earth System Science*, 129(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12040-020-01413-0>
- Kustiyo, Rokhmatuloh, Saputro, A. H., & Kushardono, D. (2021). Speckle noise reduction of Sentinel-1 SAR data using fast fourier transform temporal filtering to monitor paddy field area. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 739(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/739/1/012086>
- Lazecky, M., Canaslan Comut, F., Bakon, M., Qin, Y., Perissin, D., Hatton, E., Spaans, K., Gonzalez Mendez, P. J., Guimaraes, P., De Sousa, J. J. M., Kocich, D., & Ustun, A. (2016). *Concept of an effective Sentinel-1 Satellite SAR Interferometry System*. www.sciencedirect.com/locate/elsevier.com/locate/
- Lazecky, M., Fang, J., Hooper, A., & Wright, T. (2022). Improved Phase Unwrapping Algorithm Based on Standard Methods. *IGARSS 2022 - 2022 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 743–746. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS46834.2022.9884337>
- Li, S., Xu, W., & Li, Z. (2022). Review of the SBAS InSAR Time-series algorithms, applications, and challenges. *Geodesy and Geodynamics*, 13(2), 114–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geog.2021.09.007>
- Luo, X., Wang, C., & Shen, P. (2020). Polarimetric Stationarity Omnibus Test (PSOT) for Selecting Persistent Scatterer Candidates with Quad-Polarimetric SAR Datasets. *Sensors*, 20(6), 1555. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20061555>
- Luo, Z., Yu, J., & Liu, Z. (2019). The super-resolution reconstruction of SAR image based on the improved FSRCNN. *The Journal of Engineering*, 2019(19), 5975–5978. <https://doi.org/10.1049/joe.2019.0324>
- Manago, N., Hongo, C., Sofue, Y., Sigit, G., & Utoyo, B. (2020). Transplanting Date Estimation Using Sentinel-1 Satellite Data for Paddy Rice Damage Assessment in Indonesia. *Agriculture*, 10(12), 625. <https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture10120625>
- Marwanza, I., Anugrahadi, A., Sumotarto, U., Kurniawati, R., Fitra Yuda, H., & Nugraheni, R. (2023). Land Subsidence and Geotechnical Impact of Jakarta Kota Area. *Indonesian Journal Of Urban And Environmental Technology*, 6(2), 145–164. <https://doi.org/10.25105/urbanenvirotech.v6i2.13981>
- Masolele, R. N., De Sy, V., Herold, M., Marcos Gonzalez, D., Verbesselt, J., Gieseke, F., Mullissa, A. G., & Martius, C. (2021). Spatial and temporal deep learning methods for deriving land-use following deforestation: A pan-tropical case study using Landsat time series. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 264. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2021.112600>
- Morishita, Y. (2021). Nationwide urban ground deformation monitoring in Japan using Sentinel-1 LiCSAR products and LiCSBAS. *Progress in Earth and Planetary Science*, 8(1), 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40645-020-00402-7>
- Morishita, Y. (2022). Effective unwrapping of complicated phases by exploiting multiple interferograms: a case study of the 2016 Kumamoto earthquake. *Earth, Planets and Space*, 74(1), 33. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40623-022-01595-5>

- Morishita, Y., Lazecky, M., Wright, T. J., Weiss, J. R., Elliott, J. R., & Hooper, A. (2020). LiCSBAS: An open-source insar time series analysis package integrated with the LiCSAR automated sentinel-1 InSAR processor. *Remote Sensing*, *12*(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12030424>
- Ng, A. H. M., Ge, L., Li, X., Abidin, H. Z., Andreas, H., & Zhang, K. (2012). Mapping land subsidence in Jakarta, Indonesia using persistent scatterer interferometry (PSI) technique with ALOS PALSAR. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, *18*(1), 232–242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2012.01.018>
- Perissin, D. (2016). Interferometric SAR multitemporal processing: Techniques and applications. In *Remote Sensing and Digital Image Processing* (Vol. 20, pp. 145–176). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-47037-5_8
- Perissin, D. (2022). *The SAR PROcessing tool by periZ*. <https://www.sarproz.com>.
- Perissin, D., Jarocińska, A., De Jong, S. M., & Schaepman, M. 2016. *Multitemporal Remote Sensing: Methods and Application*. <http://www.springer.com/series/6477>
- Perissin, D., Wang, Z., & Wang, T. (2011). The SARPROZ InSAR tool for urban subsidence/man-made structure stability monitoring in China. *Engineering Purdue*.
- Potin, P., Rosich, B., Miranda, N., & Grimont, P. (2016). Sentinel-1 Mission Status. *Procedia Computer Science*, *100*, 1297–1304. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2016.09.245>
- Putri, R. F., Bayuaji, L., Sumantyo, J. T. S., & Kuze, H. (2013). Terrasar-X DInSAR for land deformation detection in Jakarta Urban area, Indonesia. *Journal of Urban and Environmental Engineering*, *7*(2), 195–205. <https://doi.org/10.4090/juee.2013.v7n2.195205>
- Ren, W., Song, J., Tian, S., & Zhang, X. (2015). Estimation of the Equivalent Number of Looks in SAR Images Based on Singular Value Decomposition. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, *12*(11), 2208–2212. <https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2015.2457334>
- Shimada, M. (2019). *Imaging from Spaceborne and Airborne SARs, Calibration, and Applications* (1st ed., Vol. 1). Taylor & Francis Group.
- Shouhei, O., Nana, J., Hiromichi, H., Daisuke, H., & Takakazu, I. (2021). Monitoring Infrastructure with Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) Satellite Service for Safe and Secure Society. *Special Issue on Social Infrastructure That Guarantees Safety, Security, Fairness, and Efficiency*, *16*(1).
- Solórzano, J. V., Mas, J. F., Gallardo-Cruz, J. A., Gao, Y., & Fernández-Montes de Oca, A. (2023). Deforestation detection using a spatio-temporal deep learning approach with synthetic aperture radar and multispectral images. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, *199*, 87–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2023.03.017>
- Sukmawati, R., Muhammad Waqar, M., & Sri Sumantyo, J. T. (2021). *Land subsidence estimation using DinSAR method ALOS PALSAR image in Padang City West Sumatra, Indonesia*. *14*(1), 41–49.
- Sumantyo, J. T. S., Setiadi, B., Perissin, D., Shimada, M., Mathieu, P.-P., Urai, M., & Abidin, H. Z. (2016). Analysis of Coastal Sedimentation Impact to Jakarta Giant Sea Wall Using PSI ALOS PALSAR. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, *13*(10), 1472–1476. <https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2016.2592940>
- Suroso, D. S. A., & Firman, T. (2018). The role of spatial planning in reducing exposure towards impacts of global sea level rise case study: Northern coast of Java, Indonesia. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, *153*, 84–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2017.12.007>

- Usai, S. (2001). *A New Approach for Longterm Monitoring of Deformations by Differential SAR Interferometry*. Delft University Press.
- Usai, S. (2002). A least-squares approach for long-term monitoring of deformations with differential SAR interferometry. *IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*, 1247–1250. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IGARSS.2002.1025903>
- Wang, S., Zhang, S., Huang, X., An, J., & Chang, L. (2019). A Highly Efficient Heterogeneous Processor for SAR Imaging. *Sensors*, *19*(15), 3409. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s19153409>
- Welikanna, D. R., Susaki, J., & Jin, S. (2021). InSAR Analysis Of Terrain Deformation Due To An Ongoing Series Of Collapse Earthquakes In The Central Highlands Of Sri Lanka. *The 42nd Asian Conference on Remote Sensing (ACRS2021)*.
- Widodo, J., Arief, R., Dinanta, G. P., Setyaningrum, N., Setiyoko, A., Putra, A. P., Oktaviani, A., Wisyanto, Santoso, E. W., Hidayat, N., Awaluddin, Kurniawan, F., Pradono, M. H., Razi, P., Izumi, Y., & Sri Sumantyo, J. T. (2022). Time Series Land Subsidence Analysis Based on Persistent Scattered Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar Method of Jakarta City Region Using Terra SAR X Spaceborne Data. *2022 International Conference on Radar, Antenna, Microwave, Electronics, and Telecommunications (ICRAMET)*, 106–113. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRAMET56917.2022.9991211>
- Widodo, J., Herlambang, A., Sulaiman, A., Razi, P., Yohandri, Perissin, D., Kuze, H., & Sri Sumantyo, J. T. (2019). Land subsidence rate analysis of Jakarta Metropolitan Region based on D-InSAR processing of Sentinel data C-Band frequency. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, *1185*, 012004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1185/1/012004>
- Xu, H., Chen, F., & Zhou, W. (2021). A comparative case study of MTInSAR approaches for deformation monitoring of the cultural landscape of the Shanhaiguan section of the Great Wall. *Heritage Science*, *9*(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40494-021-00543-y>
- Yu, G., Liang, J., Fan, W., So, H. C., & Zhou, D. (2022). Autofocus algorithms with phase error correction for synthetic aperture radar imagery. *Digital Signal Processing*, *130*, 103692. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsp.2022.103692>